

Thesis on

Identifying International Business Strategies of PRAN-RFL Group in India

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Letter of Transmittal

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Subject: Letter of Transmittal

Dear Sir,

As per the requirements for the completion of the course, OSL 406: International Business, this thesis paper has been prepared by us on “**Identifying International Business Strategies of PRAN-RFL Group in India**”. The thesis paper focuses on the implementation of some of the key elements in international business. During this assignment, we were able to relate the theories that we were taught in class to the **PRAN-RFL** Company and understand how these theories are practiced in real-life situations. The thesis paper is submitted to you for examination on August 4th, 2022. We thank you for giving us this opportunity to learn and enhance our knowledge.

Thank you.

Yours sincerely,

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We are immensely grateful to **Mr. Omar Faruk** (Head of Marketing-Brand, Pran-RFL group) for sharing his pearls of wisdom and insight with us during primary research.

Executive Summary

PRAN-RFL group has been operating in Bangladesh as one of the most profitable companies for many years, and it has been a pioneer in the agro-processed industry because, during that time, there were few companies that were catering to this industry. Their motto is to generate employment and acquire dignity and self-respect for Bangladeshi competitors. Its mission and vision are to eliminate poverty and develop the agricultural sector in Bangladesh. PRAN-RFL group is also one of the most successful companies in Bangladesh in penetrating the global market successfully. PRAN is operating its business in the dynamic global market where PRAN products are regularly being exported and have had some great success. PRAN products are exported to around 145 countries with the aim of joining the global business and creating a strong entity for Bangladesh on the world's economic map. The Indian market is one of the largest markets for the export of PRAN products, and PRAN has created a strong entity in the Indian market for several years.

This report focuses on PRAN's international business and PRAN's international strategies to become the country's largest exporter to the Indian market. Also, several issues are highlighted in this report regarding how PRAN operates in dynamic markets like India. A detailed analysis of the group is done to give a clear picture of where PRAN stands and how it can overcome its weaknesses by combining its strengths and opportunities.

Table of Contents

Letter of Transmittal	1
Acknowledgement	2
Executive Summary	3
History of Pran-RFL	5
Operations of Pran-RFL	5
Methodology	6
Source of Data	6
Primary Sources	6
Secondary Sources	6
The Political Economy of India	7
How India is affecting Pran-RFL's Business Operations	7
Sensitivity analysis (SWOT & BoP)	8
STRENGTH	8
WEAKNESSES	9
OPPORTUNITIES	9
THREATS	10
Balance of Payment	10
International Expansion	13
Export	13
Greenfield Venture	13
Business Venture	14
Strategic Alliances	14
Pran's International Strategy	15
Problems faced in the Indian Market	17
Global Effects	17
Legal Effects	17
Findings and Recommendations	17
Conclusion	18
References	19

History of Pran-RFL

“**Programme for Rural Advancement Nationally**” and “**Rangpur Foundry Limited**” or most commonly known as PRAN-RFL group is currently one of the most admired foods, beverage & plastic industrial conglomerate & market leaders in Bangladesh. It began its activities mainly with the Foundry business and gradually diversified into Light Engineering, PVC Fittings, Plastics, Food and Beverage, and Agro-Processing. When PRAN began its activity in 1980, it became Bangladesh’s largest grower and processor of fruits and vegetables, and in 1981, when PRAN and RFL (with cast iron (CI) items) merged together, it became one of the greatest business groups in Bangladesh.

Amjad Khan Chowdhury was the founder of the company, and now his son, **Ahsan Khan Chowdhury**, has been appointed as the **Chairman** and **Chief Executive Officer** of Pran-RFL Group for the last seven years. Since its inception, PRAN has been associated with contract farming and procures raw materials directly from the farmers, which are processed in their modern and hygienic factories to the highest quality and international standards. The brand PRAN has set up itself in every category of food and beverage and other industries and can boost a product range from juices, carbonated drinks, confectionery, snacks, and spices, to even dairy products. The other group of the company- “RFL”—was combined with PRAN with the objective of ensuring pure drinking water and affordable irrigation instruments for improving rural life with its wide extent of CI items like pumps, tube wells, bearings, and gas stoves, etc.

Operations of Pran-RFL

The founder of PRAN –RFL Bangladesh Limited is known as the managing director. The management staff of the company **consists of six layers**, starting from junior managers(who are local managers) to managers in grade 5 (who are PRAN-RFL managers). Apart from this, the company also hires non-management staff as well as operatives to work in the factories.

PRAN—RFL Bangladesh Limited has four departments to carry out all the organizational functions. The respective directors' heads are heads of all departments. These departments are diagrammed below:

Figure 1: PRAN-RFL's Organizational Structure

Methodology

The study covers the overall operational activities of **Pran-RFL** which exclusively go through the Indian market. Moreover, the inception of the group of industries and its prospects in Bangladesh. This paper is presented to get an understanding of how this market-leading group in Bangladesh is shaping its journey outside of Bangladesh and how it is transforming towards excellence. The information collected for this study is both from *primary and secondary sources*.

Source of Data

The study was conducted based on both primary and secondary data. The sources of that data are stated below:

Primary Sources

The primary data was collected by interviewing Mr. Omar Faruk, working as Head of Marketing (Brand), who provided us with valuable insights and information.

Secondary Sources

The secondary data was collected from the following sources:

- ❖ Various research journals of different research organizations
- ❖ Web pages
- ❖ Textbooks and other internal publications of the company

The Political Economy of India

India established itself as a free and independent nation in 1947, and it has become one of the fastest growing countries in the world since the liberalization of the economy in the 1990s. Liberalization means liberating the country's economic policies with the goal of making it a more attractive market for expanding privatization and foreign investment.

Former Prime Minister Narasimha Rao initiated the liberalization of India's economy in 1991. **When India faced a loan default crisis in 1991, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) bailed it out with a \$1.8 billion loan**, which in return demanded reforms. The reforms made it easier for international trade and investment. The reforms included reduced tariffs and interest rates, which ended public monopolies and allowed foreign direct investment into the country.

Since then, India has progressed a lot toward a free market economy with increased financial liberalization, accompanied by increases in life expectancy, literacy rate, food security, etc.

According to the World Bank's Global Economic Prospects Report, India is now the second largest and fastest growing economy after China, and it has moved towards a market-based economy. According to the World Bank, **India has recorded a GDP growth rate of 8.9 percent in 2021.**

How India is affecting Pran-RFL's Business Operations

As India lifted its ban on direct investment from Bangladesh, this became a huge opportunity for Bangladesh as well as India. One of Bangladesh's leading processed food and beverage companies, **Pran-RFL, has established its first foreign factory in the north-eastern state of Tripura, India at a targeted investment of Rs.200 crore.**

The Pran Company has been allotted the land by the Tripura Government where 500 people have been employed. As Tripura is close to Bangladesh, there is a similarity in lifestyle, culture, and economy between the two countries, and it is easier to transport raw materials from Bangladesh to Tripura. The Northeast region of India is an attractive market for Pran with a growing economy. The Indian government has

been in favor of Pran's company by providing them with needed facilities such as banking, electricity, and other infrastructure.

Pran's products, such as mango drinks and potato crackers, have become popular among local consumers. The company has **penetrated 25 states** in India. Nearly 35% of the company's total exports are to India. The export of agro-based products in India has increased by around **10 percent each year**.

Sensitivity analysis (SWOT & BoP)

STRENGTH

Image of the brand: Pran has been operating for a substantial amount of time. PRAN has been able to capture the attention of millions of customers. It created a fine and well-defined position among its customer base. In many cases, it has outsmarted its rival in terms of creating a brand preference.

Reviving consumer products with small innovations: although there are many competitors in this segment, PRAN has been able to differentiate by adding small but significant changes. For example, PRAN "Potata", where the debate goes on whether it's a biscuit or chips.

Extensive Quality Control: With very few exceptions, PRAN has consistently been able to maintain superior quality, whether it's in the domestic market or export market.

Values and ethos: Values of PRAN largely encompass remaining profitable in the market by providing quality products that result in good returns for the investor.

Customer Satisfaction: The wide range of products that are offered by PRAN results in better customer service. Customer satisfaction is also generated by affordable products.

Government support: As PRAN is one of the biggest exporters of food and agricultural products, it has always had the government by its side. By giving export subsidies and tariffs on foreign competitors, the government is trying to help companies like PRAN grow in the export market.

First mover's advantage: As PRAN was established in 1981, it got a first mover advantage in a newly established country, and the food and beverage industry was

nascent for internal and external competitors. It can be said that PRAN is still enjoying the first movers' advantage with its new product launch in the market and it can produce it cheaply in Bangladesh and export it to India.

Market share: PRAN AMCL is trying to hold a major share in the food processing industry in India. Especially in the Fruit Drinks section.

WEAKNESSES

Limited decision-making capacity: PRAN Company is monitored by agricultural marketing companies and it follows the rules and regulations. So PRAN can not respond to sudden change without the decision of AMCL.

Under the current market scenario, where the market is volatile, it is very challenging to keep a constant price as the price of raw materials often fluctuates a lot.

Per capita consumption is low: Consumer products do well where the customers have an above-average consumer consumption level. Where the buying power is greater. As most of the Indians in the rural region do not have good purchasing power, it is not always possible to reach the peak performance of PRAN's potential.

Lack of infrastructure: To cover the vast Indian market, PRAN will require a much stronger supply chain network. Due to poor supply chain structures, often the profit is minimized to some extent.

External threats: Too much competition from international organizations and both Indian producers; for example, Rasna.

Lack of product awareness: Due to a lack of proper marketing campaigns, PRAN often fails to gain the attention of its actual customers.

OPPORTUNITIES

Contribution to the GDP: By exporting goods to India, PRAN is greatly contributing to the economy of Bangladesh.

Growing number of customers: As the number of customers grows in India, it looks promising. It can be said that if PRAN consistently continues to develop its

product line and places it in the right market segment, it will enjoy a wide array of customers.

Increased awareness of the customer: Healthy and environmentally friendly products can help attract customers who are being more cautious.

Shifting food habits: With proper market research, PRAN will be able to address the new growing habits that the customers are acquiring and cater to their needs.

Employment creation: With the number of operations PRAN does, it requires a lot of workers at different levels. which would generate employment both in India and Bangladesh and strengthen their economic ties.

THREATS

Increasing Competition: Even though PRAN is expanding faster, more and more competitors are willing to join the market in the same segment where PRAN is serving its customers. For example, PRAN's situation in the dairy segment is already threatened by other internal players in the Indian market. It is very difficult to compete in that segment. Many players have already exited the Indian dairy market due to fierce competition.

Price as a competing factor: As PRAN is competing outside its home country, its product faces an intense price battle with companies inside India.

Rise of substitute products: The rise of substitute products can threaten PRAN's position in the Indian market.

Political Situation: Conducting business in the Indian subcontinent is tough on a large scale without favor from the ruling party. It can be done both passively and actively. For example, the ruling party is in favor of a company that is a competitor to PRAN, in that the competitor will get the advantage.

Balance of Payment

The balance of payment has always been negative for Bangladesh when it comes to trade with India. The tables and graphs mentioned below show a comparison between the two countries' balances of payment:

Bangladesh's trade with India (in million dollars)	Export by BD	Imported by BD
FY 10-11	304.63	3213.7
FY 11-12	512.51	4569.2
FY 12-13	498.42	4743.3
FY 13-14	563.97	4776.8
FY 14-15	456.63	6034.8

As it can be seen that the way imports from India have increased, very little has changed when it comes to the export amount of Bangladesh. which resulted in a severe trade deficit.

On the other hand, it is visible that the amount of export by PRAN to India is increasing by a substantial amount with each year. Compared to other export destinations, the Indian market seems more promising for India.

Processed food export by PRAN (In Million \$)	India	Rest of the world
FY 10-11	15.5	35.43
FY 11-12	21.52	52.52
FY 12-13	31.4	67.13
FY 13-14	36.8	79.63
FY 14-15	49.15	95.21

If PRAN Group can continue to excel in the Indian market, it can definitely help the government to adjust the balance of payment with India a little bit.

International Expansion

Expanding internationally means a company can produce more products and can do business globally. There are many opportunities and barriers to expanding business internationally. There are several ways to expand businesses, such as exports, wholly owned subsidiaries, acquisitions, licensing, etc. A company needs to find the perfect and best-fit strategy to enter a foreign market. The difference in taste varies among countries, so a company needs to select the best way to serve that foreign market. **Pran RFL started its international business by exporting.**

Export

A manufacturing company starts expanding business by exporting and then switches to other modes. Pran RFL started its international business by exporting. The Pran Company is one of the largest exporters in Bangladesh. Pran has a global customer base of around **300 million**. Pran currently exports nearly 500 products, including juices, drinks, spices, biscuits, etc. Also, Pran is currently exporting to around 145 countries. Pran entered the Indian market in 2009. Pran is the first company that is exporting products to India by waterway. Pran has a huge goal of export and that increases its growth in the international market. **One of the goals of PRAN is to export 2 billion by 2030 (Staff Correspondent, n.d.).**

Figure 2: Export of Pran

Greenfield Venture

After achieving a huge export market, Pran started to expand by greenfield acquisition. Some major greenfield acquisitions of PRAN include PRAN-RFL Group,

PRAN Beverages (India), and Pranfoods. As India has lifted its ban on Bangladeshi

investment, it has been beneficial for Bangladeshi companies. **Pran has FDI in India and is the first company in Bangladesh that build a foreign plant in India.** Initially, it produced jellies and drinks. There are some reasons behind Pran's greenfield acquisition.

- Pran can sell products at a cheaper rate in India.
- Pran can increase efficiency in producing products.
- Pran also meets the demand of local Indian customers.

Bangladesh and India have similar cultural advantages, which gives Pran some advantages.

Business Venture

Many multinational companies have complex business venture models. But Pran's company's business model is not a complex one. Pran's main strategy to expand globally includes exports of agro-processed products. The Pran Company's major venture is franchising and licensing. Pran gives franchises and licenses to international sellers to sell their products in the domestic market. This is done in two ways, and these are:

- Pran directly contacts superstores in foreign markets. For example, if Pran contacts the superstore in the Indian market and goes into a contract with them, they agree to sell **Pran's product** and keep their shelves stocked up.
- Pran set up a separate dealership program. In this dealership program, the local dealers send proposals to Pran. Pran evaluates them and selects dealers who are a perfect fit for them. Then Pran exports these products to these dealers, and these dealers sell them in the foreign market.

Strategic Alliances

The main strategy of any business is **to maximize its profitability**. The business also needs to make sure they are creating value for the customer, which ensures profitability and also business growth. This value creation actually helps customers differentiate one company from another, and this is a very important thing in international business.

Figure 3: Enterprise Valuation

The Pran company's main strategy is to cut costs as much as possible. To reduce costs, they use a strategy where they locate their production house in a low-wage rate area, and they also achieve the learning effect. By moving into a low-wage location, Pran can reduce the cost of production, and that will increase its profitability. Pran exports to 118 countries and is also trying to enter new markets to increase its profit growth. So, overall, Pran adopts the low-cost strategy. They are creating value for the customer by lowering their production costs, which increases their profitability.

Pran's International Strategy

International business is full of competition. And to secure a position in this fierce competition, every company needs an international strategy. There are two things that make an international strategy, which are the pressure of cost and the pressure of local responsiveness. There are basically four strategies based on local responsiveness and cost reduction. The global standardization strategy, transitional strategy, international strategy, and localization strategy

The Strategy of International Business

Figure 4: Pran's International Strategy

PRAN adopts the global standardization strategy. This means PRAN has a high cost of pressure but low local responsiveness. In globalization standard strategy companies focus on profit growth by the economics of scale, learning effect in short cost reduction. By adopting this strategy, Pran uses some standardized products across the global market. So PRAN uses the same kinds of products for all of the country, and to increase profitability, they try to reduce the cost of the products. For example, Pran produces "**Potata**" biscuits and exports them to India and all other countries. They do not change the biscuit's taste or anything else. In simple terms, they depend on a minimal level of customization for their products.

Problems faced in the Indian Market

Global Effects

Ongoing global competition has resulted from fierce competition. It puts severe risk for native producers and is a threat to the national interest. Similarly, the vast Indian market is already preoccupied with the presence of well-known global brands. As a result, the Indian government is slowly lifting trade barriers to protect its economy. The presence of global brands is putting tough acid tests on Pran-RFL products.

Legal Effects

If the Indian government introduces any sort of tax or if it introduces new import limits, then it will be really tough for Pran to survive in this adverse situation.

Besides, there is very little scope for product differentiation and higher trade margins offered by other competitors. Low-priced local brands and lookalikes are mushrooming in some major towns.

Findings and Recommendations

Because of its high growth rate of GDP and other factors, India is now a lucrative economy. We found that:

1. Pran is trying to focus more on export strategy than entry strategy
2. The company has some products on which it is now stable in the market, such as Pran Frooto Juice, Pran-UP, RFL plastics, plywood, etc.
3. As a well-established company, Pran-RFL group needs to strengthen its position in the Indian market through which it competes in the market and try to become unique in those areas like- strong distribution channel, human resources, etc.
4. The entry strategies such as- licensing and franchising through different distribution channels need to be implemented and well monitored
5. A joint Venture strategy can bring them enormous possibilities to sustain their footprints
6. CSR activities can position them in the good eyes of netizens.
7. Creative advertising and a strong presence in the mass media can establish their good brand visibility.

Conclusion

This paper has shed light on interesting facts about the Pran-RFL group's operations. It provided a glimpse of how politically diversified the Indian economy is and how this group is transforming its journey towards excellence. Being a participant in international business is not an easy task. In order to stay competitive, the Pran-RFL group needs to always be updated with products and better services.

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